

Modeling of Exhaust Emission (Vehicular/Industrial) for Assessing the Air Quality in Bhopal City Using Artificial Neural Network

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Abstract

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of vehicular and industrial exhaust emissions in Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, utilizing artificial neural networks (ANNs) to model and assess air quality. Over a 1500-day observational period, key pollutants including PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NH₃, NO_x, CO, O₃, and SO₂ were monitored to evaluate their impact on the Air Quality Index (AQI). The findings indicate significant fluctuations in pollutant levels, notably during times of high traffic and industrial activity, which correlate with poor AQI ratings. The predictive models demonstrated a satisfactory performance in capturing the overall trends. This research highlights the necessity for ongoing monitoring and the integration of additional variables, such as meteorological data and traffic patterns, to enhance predictive accuracy. The insights gained from this study underscore the importance of effective mitigation strategies to improve air quality and public health in urban environments. Future work will expand upon these findings by exploring emissions from various sectors and increasing the geographical scope of the analysis.

Keywords: Vehicular emissions, industrial emissions, artificial neural networks (ANN), air quality index (AQI).

1. Introduction

Industrial and vehicular emissions are significant contributors to air pollution, posing serious risks to human health and the environment. Industries release a variety of pollutants, including sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), particulate matter (PM), and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) during manufacturing processes. These emissions can lead to the formation of smog and acid rain, adversely affecting air quality and ecosystems. On the other hand, vehicles, especially those powered by fossil fuels, emit greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide

(CO₂) and pollutants such as carbon monoxide (CO) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). The increasing number of vehicles on the road exacerbates these emissions, contributing to urban air quality deterioration and respiratory diseases. Mitigating these emissions through cleaner technologies, regulatory measures, and public transportation improvements is crucial for promoting sustainable development and protecting public health. The regulatory landscape surrounding industrial and vehicular emissions has evolved significantly, with stricter standards being implemented globally to curb air pollution (European Commission, 2022). These regulations have prompted manufacturers to invest in cleaner technologies and more efficient engines (Smith et al., 2021). However, compliance with these regulations remains a challenge, particularly for older vehicles that lack modern emission control technologies (Baker et al., 2023).

Considering the above mentioned facts, present research work is dedicated to the modeling of vehicular and industrial exhaust emissions for accessing air quality. For this purpose, artificial neural network approach has been proposed. According to Kalogirou (2001), artificial neural networks are widely accepted as a technology offering an alternative way to tackle complex and ill-defined problems. They can learn from examples, are fault tolerant in the sense that they are able to handle noisy and incomplete data are able to deal with non-linear problems and, once trained, can perform prediction and generalization at high speed. The targeted city for the research work is Bhopal, the capital of Madhya Pradesh.

Following points represent the objectives of the research work:

- a) To monitor the concentrations PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NH₃, NO_x, CO, O₃, and SO₂. and
- b) To perform ambient air quality monitoring for evaluating the Air Quality Index (AQI).

2. Literature Review

The present section focuses on the academic aspects of the research and concludes with the investigated gaps in the research.

2.1 Contributions of Researchers in the Proposed Field

Present section presents the contributions of researchers in the investigating the applications of ANN in modeling exhaust emissions, as follows.

- **Guttikunda (2024)**

This research presents a cleaned and open-access vehicle stock database for India, along with a detailed methodology for constructing and maintaining a dynamic in-use vehicle age distribution database for future years.

- **Piccoli et al. (2024)**

The researchers suggest a three-phase adaptable modeling framework that includes a traffic model, an emission model, and an air quality model. Additionally, an optional fourth module can be incorporated to assess the impact of atmospheric pollution on the health of the local population.

- **Toro et al. (2024)**

The aim of the research paper is to evaluate how incorporating current real-world measurements of on-road NH₃ emission rates influences the simulation of NH₃ and PM_{2.5} concentrations in urban environments.

- **Mbandi et al. (2023)**

The researchers developed a comprehensive inventory of greenhouse gases and air pollutants from road transport to examine energy emissions under various policy scenarios for Kenya's road transport sector.

- **Khreis et al. (2022)**

In this paper, the researchers reported on the performance and the linear calibration of readings from 12 commercial low-cost sensors co-located at a regulatory air quality monitoring site in Dallas, Texas, for 18 continuous measurement months. Commercial AQY1 sensors were used, and their reported readings of O₃, NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ were assessed against a regulatory monitor.

- **Hosamani et al. (2021)**

In this work, the thermal performance characteristics and emissions of VCR, one cylinder compression ignition (CI) engine fuelled with a mixture of two biodiesel in a blend with diesel has been assessed by using ANNs.

- **Shetty et al. (2020)**

In this paper, the researchers reported that problem with the automobile engines continues to increase in a very large scale.

- **Mudway et al. (2019)**

In this paper, the researchers reported that low emission zones (LEZ) are an increasingly common, but unevaluated, intervention aimed at improving urban air quality and public health. Researchers investigated the impact of London's LEZ on air quality and children's respiratory health.

- **Dominguez-Saez et al. (2018)**

The objective of this study is the development and evaluation of two models to predict instantaneous exhaust emissions of CO₂, NO_x, particle number concentration and geometric mean diameter in accumulation mode (30–560 nm) and in nucleation mode (5.6–30 nm) of a 2.0 euro 4 diesel engine fueled with pure diesel and animal fat in different proportions.

- **He et al. (2017)**

This study analyzed the air pollution characteristics and their relation to multi-scale meteorological conditions during 2014–2015 in 31 provincial capital cities in China.

2.1 Gaps in the Research

Following points represent the gaps investigated during the survey of available literature:

- a) There is very limited number of research papers available which focus on the research on the investigations on air quality due to exhaust emissions;
- b) There is also a very limited research papers available which has focuses on the investigations on air quality of different cities of Madhya Pradesh.

Considering the research gaps the title of the research work has been proposed as **Modeling of Exhaust Emission (Vehicular/Industrial) For Assessing the Air Quality in Bhopal City Using Artificial Neural Network.**

3. Solution Methodology

The present section is devoted to the details of technique used to solve the research problem as well as the software used, the details of which are presented in upcoming sub-sections.

3.1 Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is a concept in artificial intelligence that aims to replicate the neural network of the human brain, enabling computers to process information and make decisions in a way that resembles human cognition. This network is created by programming computers to function similarly to interconnected brain cells. The human brain contains approximately 1,000 billion neurons, with each neuron having between 1,000 and 100,000 connections. In the brain, information is stored in a distributed manner, allowing us to retrieve multiple pieces of information simultaneously, showcasing the brain's parallel processing capabilities. To grasp the architecture of an artificial neural network, it's important to understand its composition, which includes numerous artificial neurons, referred to as units, arranged in layers. An artificial neural network is typically composed of three primary layers.

Figure 3.1: Artificial Neural Networks Architecture (www.javapoint.com)

a) Input Layer:

As the name suggests, it accepts inputs in several different formats provided by the programmer.

b) Hidden Layer:

The hidden layer presents in-between input and output layers. It performs all the calculations to find hidden features and patterns.

c) Output Layer:

The input goes through a series of transformations using the hidden layer, which finally results in output that is conveyed using this layer.

The artificial neural network takes input and computes the weighted sum of the inputs and includes a bias. This computation is represented in the form of a transfer function.

$$\sum_{i=1} W_i * X_i + b \quad (3.1)$$

It determines weighted total is passed as an input to an activation function to produce the output. Activation functions choose whether a node should fire or not. Only those who are fired make it

to the output layer. There are distinctive activation functions available that can be applied upon the sort of task we are performing.

3.2 MATLAB

MATLAB, short for "Matrix Laboratory," is a high-level programming language and environment designed primarily for numerical computing and data visualization. Developed by MathWorks, it provides users with an interactive platform for performing complex mathematical calculations, developing algorithms, and analyzing data. MATLAB's extensive library of built-in functions allows for efficient handling of matrices and arrays, making it particularly useful in fields such as engineering, mathematics, and scientific research. Users can create scripts and functions to automate tasks, visualize data through various types of plots, and implement algorithms for simulations and modeling. Additionally, MATLAB supports toolboxes that extend its capabilities in specialized areas like signal processing, image processing, control systems, and machine learning. Its user-friendly interface and powerful computational tools make MATLAB a popular choice for academic and industry applications, enabling researchers and engineers to solve problems and develop innovative solutions effectively.

4. Case Study

This section is dedicated to providing a comprehensive implementation of the various solution methodology techniques to the case problem, the details of which are presented in upcoming sub-sections.

4.1 Implementation of Solution methodology techniques on the Case Problem

Table 4.1 represents the details of solution methodology implementation, used to solve the research problem:

Figure 4.1: Implementation of Solution Methodology techniques to the Research Problem

Following steps present the details of implementation of solution methodology techniques on the research problem:

- a) First of all, after performing the survey of available literature, and investigations on gaps in the research and objectives of research, the city Bhopal (M.P) was finalized as the targeted city for research.
- b) In the subsequent phase, the collected data was input into MATLAB R2024a software to facilitate the training of an artificial neural network. The outcome of this training, generated by the software, is displayed in the following section, offering insight into how the neural

network was developed and optimized using MATLAB's advanced computational capabilities.

Figure 4.2: Network Diagram for ANN

- c) In the next step, for the purpose of training process of ANN with last five years data set was, accomplished. As the results of which values of actual parameters as well as their projections were obtained. For the purpose of understanding, the data of last two years was also plotted for obtaining comparable projection values for different parameters.

Figure 4.3 shows the details graphical representation of obtained data for the two years.

Figure 4.3: Graphical Representation of two years Data

- For the purpose of obtainment of results, the following code was used:

```
% Load the dataset containing input features and labels
%data = readmatrix('aqi_dataset.csv'); % Assuming CSV file with input features (PM2.5, PM10,
O3, NO2, SO2, CO) and AQI values
data = readmatrix('bhopal_dataset.csv');
% Split data into input features (X) and labels (y)
X = data(2:730, 1:6); % PM2.5, PM10, O3, NO2, SO2, CO
y = data(2:730, 8); % AQI values

% Randomly shuffle the data
idx = randperm(size(X, 1));
X = X(idx, :);
y = y(idx);

% Split data into training and testing sets (e.g., 80% train, 20% test)
train_ratio = 0.8;
num_train_samples = round(train_ratio * size(X, 1));

X_train = X(1:num_train_samples, :);
```

```
y_train = y(1:num_train_samples);
X_test = X(num_train_samples+1:end, :);
y_test = y(num_train_samples+1:end);

% Define the ANN architecture
num_hidden_units = 10; % Number of hidden units in the hidden layer

net = feedforwardnet(num_hidden_units);

% Train the ANN model
net = train(net, X_train', y_train');

% Evaluate the model
y_pred_train = net(X_train');
mse_train = mse(net, y_train', y_pred_train);

y_pred_test = net(X_test');
mse_test = mse(net, y_test', y_pred_test);

disp(['Mean Squared Error (Train): ', num2str(mse_train)]);
disp(['Mean Squared Error (Test): ', num2str(mse_test)]);

% Visualize the results
figure;
X = data(2:730, 1:7);
plot(X);
title('Comnined data');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
legend('PM10','PM2.5','NH3','SO2','CO','NOX','O3')
grid("on");
```

```
figure;
PM10 = data(2:730, 1);
plot(PM10,'g-')
title('PM10 vs. PM10 Predicted');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
hold on;
PM11 = data(2:1458, 9);
plot(PM11,'r--');
legend('PM10','PM10 Predicted');
grid("on");

figure;
PM10 = data(:, 1);
plot(PM10);
title('PM10');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
grid("on");

figure;
PM25 = data(:, 2);
plot(PM25,'g-');
title('PM2.5 vs. PM2.5 Predicted');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
hold on;
PM26 = data(2:1458, 10);
plot(PM26,'r--');
legend('PM25','PM25 Predicted');
```

```
grid("on");

figure;
PM25 = data(:, 2);
plot(PM25);
title('PM2.5');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
grid("on");

figure;
NH3 = data(:, 3);
plot(NH3,'g-');
title('NH3 vs. NH3 Predicted');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
hold on;
NH4 = data(2:1458, 11);
plot(NH4,'r--');
legend('NH3','NH3 Predicted');
grid("on");

figure;
NH3 = data(:, 3);
plot(NH3);
title('NH3');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
grid("on");
```

```
figure;  
SO2 = data(:, 4);  
plot(SO2,'g-');  
title('SO2 vs. SO2 Predicted');  
xlabel('Day Number');  
ylabel('Values');  
hold on;  
SO3 = data(2:1458, 12);  
plot(SO3,'r--');  
legend('SO2','SO2 Predicted');  
grid("on");
```

```
figure;  
SO2 = data(:, 4);  
plot(SO2);  
title('SO2');  
xlabel('Day Number');  
ylabel('Values');  
grid("on");
```

```
figure;  
CO = data(:, 5);  
plot(CO,'g-');  
title('CO vs. CO Predicted');  
xlabel('Day Number');  
ylabel('Values');  
hold on;  
CO2 = data(2:1458, 13);  
plot(CO2,'r--');
```

```
legend('CO','CO Predicted');
grid("on");

figure;
CO = data(:, 5);
plot(CO);
title('CO');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
grid("on");

figure;
NOX = data(:, 6);
plot(NOX,'g-');
title('NOX vs. NOX Predicted');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
hold on;
NOX2 = data(2:1458, 14);
plot(NOX2,'r--');
legend('NOX','NOX Predicted');
grid("on");

figure;
NOX = data(:, 6);
plot(NOX);
title('NOX');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
grid("on");
```

```
figure;
O3 = data(:, 7);
plot(O3,'g-');
title('O3 vs. O3 Predicted');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
hold on;
O4 = data(2:1458, 15);
plot(O4,'r--');
legend('O3','O3 Predicted');
grid("on");

figure;
O3 = data(:, 7);
plot(O3);
title('O3');
xlabel('Day Number');
ylabel('Values');
grid("on");

figure;
plot(y_train, 'b');
title('Actual AQI');
pause(1.5);
figure;
plot(y_pred_train, 'r--');
title('expected AQI');
pause(1.5);
figure;
```

```
subplot(2, 1, 1);
plot(y_train, 'b', 'LineWidth', 2);
hold on;
plot(y_pred_train, 'r--', 'LineWidth', 2);
title('Training Set: Actual vs. Predicted AQI');
xlabel('Sample');
ylabel('AQI');
legend('Actual', 'Predicted');
grid on;

subplot(2, 1, 2);
plot(y_test, 'b', 'LineWidth', 2);
hold on;
plot(y_pred_test, 'r--', 'LineWidth', 2);
title('Testing Set: Actual vs. Predicted AQI');
xlabel('Sample');
ylabel('AQI');
legend('Actual', 'Predicted');
grid on;

% Example prediction
example_input = [35, 45, 0.03, 0.02, 0.01, 0.2]; % Example input values for PM2.5, PM10, O3,
NO2, SO2, CO
aqi_prediction = net(example_input);
disp(['Predicted AQI for example input: ', num2str(aqi_prediction)]);
```

5. Results and Discussion

The present section is devoted to the details of results obtained from the research work, and their associated discussion, as presented in upcoming sub-sections.

5.1 Results

Figure 5.1 to show the results obtained from the research work.

(a) PM2.5 vs. PM2.5 Predicted

(b) PM10 vs. PM10 Predicted

(c) NH3 vs. NH3 Predicted

(d) NOX vs. NOX Predicted

(e) CO vs. CO Predicted

(f) O3 vs. O3 Predicted

(g) SO2 vs. SO2 Predicted

(g) AQI vs. AQI Predicted

Figure 5.1: Results of the Research Work

5.2 Discussion

Detailed explanation of different results obtained from the research work is presented as follows.

Figure 5.2: Actual vs Predicted PM2.5

Figure compares the actual and predicted values of PM2.5 emissions (particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or smaller), which are exhaust emissions from vehicles, over a period of approximately 1500 days, the details of which are presented as follows.

- **Model Behavior:** The prediction model performs well during stable emission periods but struggles when there are rapid changes in PM2.5 levels, particularly in capturing the exact magnitude of spikes.
- **Prediction Improvements:** The prediction model might need adjustments to better handle the extreme fluctuations or account for factors such as traffic congestion, vehicle type, or weather conditions.
- **Health and Environmental Implications:** PM2.5 is a critical pollutant due to its ability to penetrate deep into the lungs and cause health issues. Spikes in PM2.5 emissions, as observed in this data, may correspond to periods of high risk for public health and air quality.

Figure 5.3: Actual vs Predicted PM10

Figure 5.3 compares actual and predicted PM10 emissions (particulate matter with a diameter of 10 micrometers or smaller) over a time period of approximately 1500 days.

- **Model Performance:** The prediction model generally tracks the trends well, particularly when PM10 levels are more stable. However, it struggles with accurately predicting the magnitude of spikes, often overestimating PM10 concentrations during periods of high emissions. This suggests that the model may need fine-tuning to better capture the dynamics of high-emission events.

- **Improvement Opportunities:** Incorporating additional factors like weather data, traffic flow information, or specific events (e.g., construction or festivals) might improve the accuracy of the model, particularly in predicting spikes and periods of increased PM10 emissions.

Figure 5.4: Actual vs Predicted NH3

Figure 5.4 compares the actual and predicted values of NH₃ emissions (particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or smaller), which are exhaust emissions from vehicles, over a period of approximately 1500 days, the details of which are presented as follows.

- **Model Behavior:** The prediction model performs well in capturing both the general trend and specific fluctuations in NH₃ levels.
- **Data Gap:** The absence of actual NH₃ data after day 750 raises questions about data collection continuity or potential changes in measurement practices.
- **Environmental Implications:** NH₃ is a significant air pollutant contributing to particulate matter formation and ecosystem impacts. Understanding and predicting its levels is crucial for air quality management.

Figure 5.5: Actual vs Predicted NOX

Figure 5.5 compares the actual and predicted values of NOX emissions, which are exhaust emissions from vehicles, over a period of approximately 1500 days, the details of which are presented as follows.

- **Model Behavior:** The prediction model captures the general trends in NOX levels but tends to overestimate the intensity of fluctuations.
- **Data Gap:** The absence of actual NOX data after day 750 limits our ability to assess the model's long-term accuracy.
- **Environmental Implications:** NOX is a critical air pollutant contributing to smog formation and acid rain. Accurate prediction of NOX levels is essential for air quality management and public health protection.

Figure 5.6: Actual vs Predicted CO

Figure 5.6 compares the actual and predicted values of CO emissions, which are exhaust emissions from vehicles, over a period of approximately 1500 days, the details of which are presented as follows.

- **Model Behavior:** The prediction model captures the general trends in CO levels but tends to overestimate the intensity of fluctuations.
- **Data Gap:** The absence of actual CO data after day 750 limits our ability to assess the model's long-term accuracy.
- **Environmental Implications:** CO is a harmful air pollutant that can have serious health effects at high concentrations. Accurate prediction of CO levels is crucial for public health protection and air quality management.

Figure 5.7: Actual vs Predicted O3

Figure 5.7 compares the actual and predicted values of O₃ emissions, which are exhaust emissions from vehicles, over a period of approximately 1500 days, the details of which are presented as follows.

- **Model Behavior:** The prediction model captures the general trends in O₃ levels but tends to overestimate the intensity of fluctuations.
- **Data Gap:** The absence of actual O₃ data after day 750 limits our ability to assess the model's long-term accuracy.
- **Environmental Implications:** O₃ is a major component of smog and can cause respiratory issues. Accurate prediction of O₃ levels is crucial for public health protection and air quality management.

Figure 5.8: Actual vs Predicted SO2

Figure 5.8 compares the actual and predicted values of SO₂ emissions, which are exhaust emissions from vehicles, over a period of approximately 1500 days, the details of which are presented as follows.

- **Model Behavior:** The prediction model captures the general trends in SO₂ levels but tends to overestimate the intensity of fluctuations.
- **Data Gap:** The absence of actual SO₂ data after day 750 limits our ability to assess the model's long-term accuracy.
- **Environmental Implications:** SO₂ is a major air pollutant that can cause respiratory issues and contribute to acid rain. Accurate prediction of SO₂ levels is crucial for air quality management and public health protection.

Figure 5.9: Actual vs Predicted AQI

Figure 5.9 compares the actual and predicted values of AQI emissions, which are exhaust emissions from vehicles, over a period of approximately 1500 days, the details of which are presented as follows.

- **Model Behavior:** The prediction model captures the general trends and specific fluctuations in AQI levels with high accuracy.
- **Consistency:** The model's performance is consistent across both training and testing sets, suggesting good reliability.
- **Environmental Implications:** Accurate AQI predictions are crucial for public health advisories and air quality management strategies.
- **Real-time Application:** The model's ability to predict sudden spikes accurately makes it valuable for issuing timely air quality warnings.

6. Conclusion, Limitations and Future Scope of the research

The present section is devoted to the conclusion of the research work as well as observed limitations and future scope of the research, the details of which are presented in upcoming sub-sections.

6.1 Conclusion

The following points represent the conclusions drawn for different exhaust emission pollutants as well as their effect on AQI.

a) PM_{2.5} (Particulate Matter $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$):

- Trends: PM_{2.5} levels showed considerable variation, with concentrations ranging from as low as $7.59 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to as high as $203.51 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ throughout the observation period.
- Impact on AQI: Higher PM_{2.5} levels correlate strongly with poor AQI readings, often indicating severe pollution, especially during peak periods.
- Insights: Continuous monitoring and mitigation strategies are critical to managing PM_{2.5} emissions effectively, as they are major contributors to health issues.

b) PM₁₀ (Particulate Matter $\leq 10 \mu\text{m}$):

- Trends: Similar to PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ demonstrated significant fluctuations, with levels between 18.0 to $300.4 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ recorded.
- Impact on AQI: PM₁₀ spikes contribute to elevated AQI values, particularly during construction and heavy traffic times.
- Insights: Effective strategies must include controlling dust from construction sites and emissions from vehicles to lower PM₁₀ levels.

c) NH₃ (Ammonia):

- Trends: NH₃ levels were less variable compared to PM, reflecting a consistent influence from agricultural activities, particularly during fertilizer application.
- Impact on AQI: While NH₃ levels are typically lower, they can still influence aerosol formation and secondary pollutants.

- Insights: Implementing agricultural best practices could significantly mitigate NH₃ emissions, improving overall air quality.

d) NO_x (Nitrogen Oxides):

- Trends: NO_x emissions showed fluctuating trends, peaking during traffic-heavy periods.
- Impact on AQI: NO_x levels played a significant role in forming ground-level ozone, which can adversely affect air quality.
- Insights: Reducing emissions from vehicles and industrial sources is vital for controlling overall NO_x levels effectively.

e) CO (Carbon Monoxide):

- Trends: CO concentrations fluctuated based on vehicular emissions, particularly from older vehicles.
- Impact on AQI: While CO levels are typically lower, sudden spikes can occur, leading to deteriorating air quality conditions.
- Insights: Ongoing vehicle inspections and emissions regulations can help minimize CO emissions and improve air quality.

f) O₃ (Ozone):

- Trends: Ozone levels showed marked fluctuations, often correlating with warmer temperatures and increased sunlight.
- Impact on AQI: Elevated ozone levels frequently coincide with poor AQI, particularly during summer months.
- Insights: Managing precursor pollutants, such as NO_x and volatile organic compounds, is essential for controlling ozone concentrations.

g) SO₂ (Sulfur Dioxide):

- Trends: SO₂ levels varied significantly, influenced by industrial activities and occasional spikes due to natural events.
- Impact on AQI: SO₂ is a significant contributor to the overall AQI and poses health risks, especially during peak episodes.

- Insights: Enhanced regulatory measures on industrial emissions can lead to more stable and lower SO₂ levels.

h) Air Quality Index (AQI):

- Trends: Over the observed period, average AQI values ranged from “Good” to “Very Poor,” with significant fluctuations and spikes often driven by particulate matter and ozone levels.
- Insights: The model showed a generally accurate prediction of AQI trends, capturing both fluctuations and significant spikes. Continuous real-time monitoring systems and predictive modeling techniques are crucial for effective public health advisories and timely interventions.

6.2 Limitations and Future Scope of the Research

The following points represent the limitations of the research work:

- The predictive models used for estimating pollutant levels may not fully account for all contributing factors, leading to inconsistencies in forecasting spikes, especially during rapid changes in emissions;
- The research primarily focuses on Bhopal, which may limit the generalizability of findings to other regions with different industrial and environmental contexts; and
- The study may not account for all sources of emissions, such as unregulated or informal sectors, which could result in underestimating total pollutant levels.

The following points represent the future scope of the research work:

- There is a need to refine predictive models by integrating a broader range of variables, including real-time traffic data, industrial operation patterns, and demographic factors, to improve accuracy in forecasting emissions and AQI fluctuations;
- Expanding research to include multiple cities or regions with different industrial profiles and environmental conditions will allow for comparative analyses and enhance the generalizability of findings across diverse contexts; and
- Efforts should be made to identify and quantify emissions from unregulated or informal sectors. Collaborating with local industries and informal sectors could provide a more accurate picture of total emissions in the area.

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